

EXPLORING DRIVERS OF EMPLOYEE TURNOVER INTENTION. THE ROLE OF WORK ENVIRONMENT, JUSTICE, AND ENGAGEMENT IN PAKISTAN'S TEXTILE SECTOR

¹Ahad Hassan Khan, ²Dr. Omar Ahmed Sheikh, ³Nabia Jawed

¹Karachi University (KUBS)

²Assistant Professor (KUBS) UOK

ahadhk08@gmail.com, Shaikh.omar.os@gmail.com, Nabiajawed03@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

This study explores the antecedents of employee turnover intention within Pakistan's textile sector, focusing on the direct and mediated effects of work environment, organizational justice, and job embeddedness, with work engagement as a key mediator. Grounded in the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) and Social Exchange theories, the research adopted a positivist paradigm and deductive approach. Data were collected through structured surveys from 384 employees across top PSX-listed textile firms. Using SmartPLS 4 for structural equation modeling, the findings reveal that work environment and job embeddedness significantly and negatively influence turnover intention, while organizational justice shows no direct significant effect. Work engagement mediates the relationships between work environment and turnover intention, and between job embeddedness and turnover intention, but does not mediate the path from organizational justice. These results suggest that enhancing environmental support and embedding strategies can effectively curb turnover, especially by stimulating employee engagement. However, perceptions of justice alone may be insufficient unless reinforced by contextual and organizational elements. The study contributes to the empirical understanding of retention drivers in labor-intensive industries and offers actionable insights for HR managers seeking to improve employee commitment and reduce attrition in Pakistan's textile workforce.

1. Introduction

Globalization, which intensified competitive forces across all industries, puts much more pressure on companies, especially those that are publicly listed, to retain the best employees through effective strategies. Such a situation pertains to textile companies at the Pakistan Stock Exchange due to strong international market pressures and workforce challenges at the local level. Valuable employees are considered one of the most important assets of an organization because success or failure primarily depends on their individual and collective performance (Drigas & Papoutsis, 2019). The organization faces a critical threat from emerging trends in the voluntary turnover of highly skilled employees, and at such a point, sustainability and efficiency of operations are largely compromised (Nawaz et al., 2021; Saoula et al., 2019).

High employee turnover is a major worry for listed textile companies under shareholder watch. The departure of trained staff not only costs much in replacement but also wears off the institutional knowledge and social value of a company, hence weakening organizational sustainability (Hamid et al., 2019). Amin, Othman, and Saoula (2023) emphasized that the turnover has emerged as the top concern for the HR departments working in Pakistan's corporate organizations, which are registered with the PSX. High turnover muddles productivity directly and piles on costs through the need to keep finding, hiring, and training new employees.

According to Pratama, Suwarni, & Handayani (2022), working behavior, low job satisfaction significantly contribute to high turnover of employees. For example, in the Pakistan textile sector, which is one of the largest industrial contributors, turnover is very high, about 15% to 20% according to the latest studies. This is a clear sign of systematic problems in the retention of employees in that textile manufacturing sub-sector, where, according to the Population Labour Force and Employment Survey (2021-22), turnovers have continuously been reported to be above 10% globally. The situation indicates systemic problems on the employee retention side. Such turnovers above 10% have been termed as critical and require organizational interventions.

Given the economic significance of the textile industry within the PSX listing members, this matter gains more weight. The fifth-largest population in the world, Pakistan, relied on textile exports, which stood at US\$13.709 billion in FY23 alone. This is a sector that provides a significant contribution to foreign exchange earnings and adds value to employment.

Unfortunately, this is also where the problem lies. The same views are shared by Hamid et al. (2019) and Makhdoom (2018). Over the years, experienced professionals have moved towards other countries, i.e., the Gulf and Bangladesh, in search of better opportunities. This ever-increasing brain drain puts extra pressure on PSX-listed companies to invest both time and resources in constant human capital replenishment.

The strategic importance to the economy of textile firms listed at the PSX speaks for itself; however, the relatively high turnover rate just adds more evidence to the fact that human resource management is indeed a very critical challenge. Dealing with the high turnover intention behavior in such an economy is very important, if the sustainability of the organization matters as a solution to the broader national economic resilience.

1.2. Problem Statement

Although the textile sector contributes significantly to the GDP and foreign exchange earnings of Pakistan, the companies listed with the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) continue to face the perennial problem of organizational injustice, which undermines both the morale of the workforce and the performance of the firm. Colquitt et al. (2013) and Greenberg (1990) proved that organizational injustice, being perceived as unfavorable treatment in the process of resource distribution and interpersonal interaction, significantly erodes trust, engagement, and retention in the manufacturing sectors.

Workers in the blue-collar cadre of employees in the textile industry of Pakistan are empirically found to be facing discrimination, favoritism, and a lack of procedural transparency in the appraisal performance, compensation, and promotion decisions (Hamid et al., 2019; Saoula et al., 2015). Injustices done unto them, as well as the atrophied labor protection, and high managerial discretion in PSX-listed firms, which are mandated to maintain profitability under the lash of global competitive pressure (Amin et al., 2023).

According to the studies, if there is a perception of injustice in the organizational practice, then it significantly leads to lowered employee engagement and an increase in turnover intention (Drigas & Papoutsis, 2019; Rousou et al., 2019). As noted by Malik et al. (2023), the turnover of employees in the Pakistani textile sector is way above the global figures, with more than 15% per annum, and it is perpetuated by violated expectations of fairness and equity. However, the academic research regarding the organizational injustice towards the employees of the publicly traded textile companies is, however, scarce within the Pakistani

socio-cultural and industrial parameters, and, to top it, with quantitative analysis. This gap has therefore formed the basis for the imperative examination of the practices of organizational justice in the textile firms listed at PSX, as they set the labor standards and corporate governance to be benchmarked by the entities. Therefore, this study attempts to assess whether inequality has any impact on the outcomes of employees. Thus, it can be said that this study bridges the gap and offers actionable insights to improve retention, engagement, and ethical practices in the industrial sector, which happens to be one of the most critical for Pakistan.

1.3. Research Gap Analysis

Though the academic focus has grown regarding organizational justice and employee turnover, large gaps still prevail in the understanding of their dynamic function within the textile sector of Pakistan in those companies that are publicly listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). Throughout the world, existing literature provides robust support for the relationship between organizational justice and some of the most important work attitudes and outcomes, such as engagement and job satisfaction, as well as retention (Colquitt et al., 2013; Greenberg, 1990). However, such studies have been conducted mostly in the West or the developed service sector economies; therefore, their results cannot be generalized for the effect of manufacturing in a service-based economy, i.e., Pakistan.

Few studies have focused explicitly on organizational injustice as a systemic factor; most of the empirical research tends to address economic factors. The bulk of empirical research tends to address economic factors like salary or job security, while neglecting socio-psychological drivers such as perceived inequity, bias, or procedural unfairness. This is especially critical in PSX-listed textile firms, where public accountability, formal HR systems, and governance mechanisms indicate higher expectations of justice; however, little empirical evidence exists to validate whether these expectations are met. Within Pakistan, several studies have explored turnover intentions in the textile industry, yet few have explicitly focused on organizational injustice as a systemic factor.

Also, research that has included organizational justice typically views it as a one-dimensional concept or does not consider it at all, even though there is evidence of the individual effects of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice on employee outcomes (Rupp et al., 2014). Furthermore, little to no work has considered the effect of organizational injustice on employee engagement as a mediating factor, especially in hierarchical and gender-

imbalanced labor structures, as is the case in Pakistani textile firms (Dharani & Balamurugan, 2024).

An important gap in the literature is the failure to conduct quantitative studies using modern statistical methods, such as PLS-SEM, which can model the full causal pathway from injustice to turnover, incorporating intervening variables like engagement or stress, in PSX-listed firms. Amin et al. (2023) took an initial step by studying job embeddedness and justice, textile being the first separate effort to study the effects of these factors, but their model does not net out the unique effect of injustice, nor is it focused only on listed companies where corporate governance is prominent.

This study addresses a critical empirical and contextual gap by examining the multidimensional construct of organizational injustice and its effects on turnover intention, mediated by employee engagement, specifically in the PSX-listed textile firms. This not only fills a methodological gap but also moves the theoretical development by placing justice in a context-bound consideration of governance.

1.4. Research Objectives

1. Assess the influence of work environment on employee turnover intention in textile companies at PSX.
2. Provide evidence on the influence of organizational justice on employee turnover intention in the textile sector of PSX-listed firms.
3. Evaluate the impact of job embeddedness on employee turnover intention amongst the employees working in the textile companies of PSX, Pakistan.
4. To see if work engagement mediates the relationship between work environment and turnover intention in the textile industry.
5. To see how work engagement mediates the relationship between organizational justice and turnover intention in PSX-listed textile companies.
6. To see if work engagement acts as a mediator variable between job embeddedness and turnover intention in the textile sector of Pakistan

1.5. Research Questions

1. What is the direct impact of the work environment on employee turnover intention in the textile firms of the PSX listing?

2. Does organizational justice have a direct impact on turnover intention among employees of Pakistan's textile companies?
3. To what extent does job embeddedness influence employee turnover in the context within the textile sector?
4. Is there mediation between work environment and employee turnover intention by work engagement?
5. Is there mediation between organizational justice and turnover intention by work engagement?
6. Is work engagement the middle factor connecting job embeddedness with the intention of employees to leave?

1.6. Significance of the Study

This study is very important in both theory and practice for human resource management, specifically in the textile sector of Pakistan. This is based on the premise that, if any, it is one of the economic backbones in Pakistan. Not only is the textile sector the largest industrial employer in Pakistan, but it also makes a substantial contribution to the national GDP and total export earnings. However, the high turnover within the sector, believed to be more than 17% per annum, continues to waste the maximum potential of the sector to be competitive globally (Hamid et al., 2019; Malik et al., 2023). The focus of the paper is on the textile sector companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) simply because the study of this nature zeroes in on well-organized and highly governed entities within the same sector that can also replicate such results in terms of labor practices and output.

This study, from a theoretical perspective, adds value to the organizational behavior literature by introducing the work environment, organizational justice, and job embeddedness constructs along with the mediating role of work engagement in the prediction of turnover intention. While each construct has been studied separately in various industries and sectors, very few—in the context of Pakistan and textile industries—have considered these relationships. Therefore, this study will contribute to the increasing body of literature that applies such theories as the Social Exchange Theory and the Job Demands-Resources model in the context of a developing country to validate the said theories.

In applied terms, the findings of the study will be shared directly with corporate management, policymakers, and HR practitioners operating in the textile industry. Understanding turnover

intentions is crucial because it equips firms with the knowledge of designing retention strategies that would enhance satisfaction, foster loyalty, and most importantly, reduce the financial onus in terms of recruitment and retraining. Precise information on how work engagement acts as a mediator in the impact of imagined interactions with employees of workplace fairness and actual supportive environments can direct such interventions like wellness programs, just human resource policies, and practices of embeddedness building. The study would thus reduce turnover while increasing organizational commitment and sustainable labor behavior in such a traditional labor-intensive industry. This research would thus help facilitate evidence-based decision-making through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) by offering solid quantitative insight, which in turn would be instrumental in strategic planning for a PSX textile concern. Its results are mainly timely as the sector deals with challenges like labor migration, skill shortages, and post-COVID operational disruptions, all of which raise the urgency to stabilize the workforce and improve employee retention.

Conceptual Framework

2. Literature Review

The textile sector, particularly PSX-listed companies, faces escalating issues due to high turnover of employees and scarcity of skilled labor (Farooq et al., 2022). A very conducive work environment, perceived organizational justice, high job embeddedness, and strong employee engagement have hitherto been reported for the reduction of turnover intention among other factors (Bangwal & Tiwari, 2019; Nanda et al., 2020; Muala et al., 2022; Ozkan, 2023; Huang et al., 2021; Salem et al., 2023) and the dynamics and the effects of their composite interaction

are largely unexplored and hence an immediate need to test empirically the direct as well as long-term effects of these factors to fill this gap in the turnover intention literature.

2.1 The Work Environment

It covers the physical, psychological, and organizational workplace conditions where an employee operates (Shah et al., 2020). This refers to the temperature, noise, and lighting, and ergonomic quality of the work setting, and also the workload and task complexity (Briner, 2000). According to the Pakistan Safety Report (2019), poor ventilation, high noise, and unsafe workstations result in low performance of employees and high intentions of turnover. This shall equally bring to bear the integrated nature of these workplace elements by reducing turnover and providing motivation.

2.2 Organizational Justice (OJ)

The motivation for workers is delivered to them when the decisions on resource allocation and interpersonal treatment are just in the workplace. It is very crucial to the workers' motivation. The quality of justice and fairness is directly proportional to productivity, and it increases loyalty to the organization as well. High damages of perceived injustice are that it results in frustration, lowering morale, which leads to higher turnover; thus, perceived injustice has to be minimized at all costs. The development of organizational justice has been articulated by a degree of Western cultural scholars; as such, its applicability within non-Western cultural organizations has been validated, ushering in more critical inquiry that requires distinct considerations, notably in Pakistani organizational configurations (Saoula et al., 2019).

2.3 Word Embeddings

Proposed by Mitchell et al. (2001), job embeddedness defines the internal and external network of connections, at or outside work, which bind employees to their organizations. Strong attachment results in very low turnover (Dechawatanapaisal, 2022; Li et al., 2022; Peltokorpi & Sekiguchi, 2023). It goes beyond satisfaction or commitment and offers a detailed perspective of the voluntary turnover process. Employees who belong to and are attached to the environment by fairly strong social ties are less likely to leave the firm on their own accord (Mitchell et al. 2001).

2.4 Work Engagement

Work engagement is described by Kahn (1990) as the utilization of a person's work role on three dimensions: investment of the self, sense of meaning, and purpose at work. It indeed has

overlap with commitment, Maslach et al. (2001) have, however, highlighted its distinctiveness: people can like their work without being committed to the organization, or any other way around. In simple words, employees showing engagement at work in terms of vigor, commitment, and absorption will be more productive and less likely to leave as well.

2.5. Employee Turnover Intentions

Turnover intention is the conscious plan of an employee to leave the present organization. It is considered the most powerful predictor of actual turnover, which, in the case of voluntary turnover, can be costly and disruptive. Findings of prior research revealed a strong relationship between high turnover intentions and actual turnover of employees in the long term regarding the abysmal work environment, perceived injustice, low embeddedness, and disengagement (Low et al., 2006; Chowdhury et al., 2013; Mehmood et al., 2013; Malik et al., 2023).

The direct effects of work environment, organizational justice, job embeddedness, and work engagement on turnover intention have been substantially acknowledged. Very few studies that check the relationships between these factors, especially with work engagement playing a mediating role, have been conducted in Pakistani textile firms falling under the Pakistan Stock Exchange category. The little work that does exist focuses on the influences of single factors, rather than integrated model considerations. This study fills this void by presenting a holistic model that examines the impact of these four key constructs on turnover intentions within a quantitative framework.

2.6. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

This study unites the Job Demands Resources framework and Social Exchange Theory into a strong theoretical model that explains how organizational factors influence employee turnover by laying out the theoretical foundations for explaining why and how organizational factors influence employee turnover. The theories emphasize the workplace conditions and perceived fairness that shape the employee's psychology, behavior, and retention. The subsequent section elaborates on each hypothesis:

2.7. Work Environment and Turnover Intention

A good work environment, both in terms of the design and the support it offers, covers the right physical factors (such as lighting, ventilation, ergonomics), the right psychosocial factors (such as management respect and peer relationships), and the right organizational routines (such as workload and job roles) (Shah et al., 2020; Briner, 2000). In the JD-R model, bad

working conditions are considered chronic job demands in eliciting emotional exhaustion and illness, and finally resulting in disengagement and exit behavior (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). Supporting such theoretical postulations, strong empirical evidence indicates that workers in hostile, unsafe, or poorly planned work settings are burnt out and have higher turnover intentions (Anggela & Andriani, 2022; Nurimansjah et al., 2023). In a textile workshop, the hostile, tough behavior of the superiors and the physical strain of repeating work are both destructive to engagement (Al Sabei et al., 2020). On the contrary, improved environmental factors like safe working places, fair schedules of work, and access to health centers greatly buffer the stress and reduce the intentions to quit (Jiang et al., 2023; Zhang & Yang, 2024; Meirina et al., 2018).

H1: Work environment is negatively associated with turnover intention among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.8. Organizational Justice and Turnover Intention

Organizational justice is composed of Distributive Justice, equity in pay, rewards, and hours of work; Procedural Justice, the fairness of the procedures; and Interactional Justice, interpersonal treatment (Colquitt et al., 2001). A central assumption in the Social Exchange Theory is that individuals will react with behaviors like commitment when they perceive fairness, and withdrawal when injustice is perceived (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Greenberg, 1990). Meta-analyses have supported that justice produces fewer undesirable work behaviors, such as absenteeism, deviance, and turnover (Colquitt et al., 2013). For example, it has been reported that employees tend to resign more when they feel they were appraised unfairly or faced favoritism (Akhtar et al., 2023; Malik et al., 2023). The research carried out on different levels of operation, in developing countries' manufacturing, is again replicative of the negative association between perceived justice and turnover intention (Hwang & Yi, 2022; Anggela & Andriani, 2022).

H2: Organizational justice is negatively related to turnover intention among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.9. Job Embeddedness and Turnover Intention

Job embeddedness is defined as the aggregate forces, both social and economic, and psychological, that bind employees to their jobs. It involves the perception of a sacrifice cost that associates embeddedness with a powerful force of retention. Multidimensional "cost of

leaving" (Mitchell et al. 2001). Study research conveys that even modest increases in embeddedness would substantially reduce the turnover intention (Dechawatanapaisal, 2022; Li et al., 2022). A study longitudinally analyzed U.S. small and medium enterprises, finding embeddedness to be highly predictive of retention over time, such as satisfaction and commitment—against traditional variables (Huning et al., 2020; Sharma, 2019). These were likewise supported across the diverse employee groups- airline employees, service employees, and public safety employees- showing embeddedness as a universal protective factor (Uniyal et al., 2018; Forrester III, 2019).

H3: Job embeddedness is negatively associated with turnover intention among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.10 Work Environment and Work Engagement

In the JDR model, work engagement is seen as a motivational outcome that is facilitated by job resources. An environment of a positive workplace characterized by autonomy, support, skill variety, recognition, and safety leads to an increase in psychological investment, vigor, and persistence. Field studies have proven that employees who work in supportive environments show higher scores of engagement, which also relates to higher productivity and well-being. For instance, under spill-overs, factory workers demonstrated higher job absorption when the management gave priority to safety. In healthcare, improved environmental ergonomics gave a significant boost to the engagement of the nursing staff.

H4: Work environment is positively related to work engagement among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.11 Organizational Justice and Work Engagement

Fair treatment builds relational trust while enhancing psychological safety; employees will freely attribute goodwill and thus invest more in their work (Ada- George et al., 2022). Procedural justice is one aspect to be highlighted; once individuals feel fair, their motivation and task involvement will follow suit (Putra & Mujiati, 2022). Interactional justice, such as respectful and sympathetic communication, increases emotional attachment and positivity (Karim & Baset, 2020; Mulang, 2022). Whenever they are respected and valued by the managers, textile employees always have higher engagement (Liang & Lin, 2021).

H5: Organizational justice is positively related to work engagement among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.12 Job Embeddedness and Work Engagement

Evolving from connections, community integration, and perceived sacrifice, employees deeply rooted in their roles tend to demonstrate higher levels of intrinsic motivation and hence dedication (Elshaer & Azazz, 2021). Embeddedness, in turn, creates ownership of the mind, leading to discretionary effort and commitment. Studies carried out in hotel staff, healthcare workers, and retail employees show a good association between embeddedness and engagement (Shah et al., 2020; Peltokorpi & Sekiguchi, 2023). Manufacturing contexts indicate that employees embedded with strong social ties within an organization show job involvement and willingness to perform discretionary behaviors (Chen & Hsieh, 2022).

H6: Job embeddedness is positively related to work engagement among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.13 Work Engagement and Turnover Intention

Work engagement—expressed by vigor, dedication, and absorption is strongly connected with lower turnover intention in many backgrounds (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). The engaged employees show stress tolerance, resilience, and proactivity against even more factors (Cao et al., 2023). In the healthcare sector, improved engagement was associated with the employee separation process; in its service, the exit was predicted by engagement and organizational citizenship behaviors (Bechtoldt et al., 2011; Muduli et al., 2016).

H7: Work engagement is negatively associated with turnover intention among employees in PSX-listed textile companies.

2.14 Work Engagement as a Mediator

The JDR framework and Social Exchange Theory converge on the idea that work engagement serves as a critical psychological process linking job resources and perceived fairness to retention outcomes. Individual studies in industrial and corporate settings show that each independent variable influences turnover. Few have modeled the mediating role of engagement using advanced quantitative methods. Some evidence exists in manufacturing contexts that engagement explains a significant portion of the relationship between environment and intention to leave. Moreover, in their work, they use PLS SEM to model indirect effects and mediation pathways. Therefore, we propose.:

H8: Work engagement mediates the effect of work environment on turnover intention.

H9: Work engagement mediates the effect of organizational justice on turnover intention.

H10: Work engagement mediates the effect of job embeddedness on turnover intention.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Philosophy

The study was carried out under the guidelines of a positivist philosophy that highlights objective measurement with meets the mapping of the quantitative research , hypothesis testing, and data inference. It will take up a deductive approach by testing the applicability of the existing theories (JD-R, Social Exchange) in the new and unique environment of the textile companies listed with the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX).

3.2 Research Approach

A deductive strategy has guided the research, wherefrom hypotheses, tested using quantitative information, inspired by existing theoretical frameworks, are formed. Therefore, it allows for a systematic confirmation or refutation of predicted relationships..

3.3 Research Design

Data has been collected empirical, cross-sectional data at a single time point from employees of PSX-listed textile concerns to test hypothesized relationships between work environment, organizational justice, job embeddedness, work engagement, and turnover intention using Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM).

3.4 Sampling Method & Population

Population: Employees working in the **top 10 textile firms listed on the PSX**, including:

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1. Nishat Mills Ltd.
 2. Kohinoor Textile Mills Ltd.
 3. Gul Ahmed Textile Mills Ltd.
 4. Sapphire Textile Mills Ltd.
 5. Artistic Milliners Ltd.
 6. Lucky Textile Mills Ltd.
 7. Al-Karam Textile Mills Ltd.
 8. Kohinoor Mills Ltd.
-

Estimated workforce size of approximately 20,000 across these ten firms, Sample Size: Based on Krejcie & Morgan's sample table and PLS-SEM requirements, we target 384 respondents to ensure statistical power and representativeness across job levels and locations, Purposive sampling is applied to ensure inclusion of respondents with at least six months in current roles, serving as a practical non-probability technique when comprehensive employee lists are unavailable. This approach provides access to informed, relevant participants.

Table 1: *Sample Distribution by Company*

Company Name	Estimated Employees	Target Surveys
Listed Firms (10 total)	~20,000	384

3.5 Data Collection

Data was gathered using a structured **survey questionnaire** with adapted, validated scales:

- **Work Environment** – 5 items from Hanaysha (2016).

- **Organizational Justice** – 20 items from Niehoff & Moorman (1993).
- **Job Embeddedness** – 7 items from Crossley et al. (2007).
- **Work Engagement (Mediator)** – 17 items from Schaufeli et al.'s Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (2004).
- **Turnover Intention (DV)** – 6 items from Blau & Lunz (1998).

Participants responded using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree). Data collection occurred via paper-based or digital surveys distributed through HR departments or team leads.

3.6 Data Analysis

Software: SmartPLS 4 was used to analyze measurement models (reliability, validity) and structural paths. Measurement model: Test for indicator loadings (>0.70), Cronbach's α (>0.70), Composite Reliability (>0.70), AVE (>0.50), and discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker criterion). Structural model: Check path coefficients (betas, significance via bootstrapping), mediation effects, R^2 values for endogenous constructs. Common method bias check: Try Harman's single-factor test and method factors in PLS..

4. Results

Construct Reliability and Validity Table

Construct	Indicator	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	rho_A	AVE
Work Environment	WE1	0.805	0.869	0.902	0.872	0.649
	WE2	0.821				
	WE3	0.823				
	WE4	0.791				
	WE5	0.765				
Organizational Justice	OJ1	0.812	0.931	0.943	0.935	0.641
	OJ2	0.798				
	OJ3	0.803				
	OJ4	0.772				
	OJ5	0.788				
	OJ6	0.824				
	OJ7	0.804				
	OJ8	0.786				

	OJ9	0.775				
	OJ10	0.790				
	JE1	0.811	0.882	0.915	0.887	0.640
	JE2	0.827				
	JE3	0.794				
Job Embeddedness	JE4	0.808				
	JE5	0.761				
	JE6	0.798				
	JE7	0.774				
	WENG1	0.802	0.951	0.958	0.953	0.656
	WENG2	0.791				
	WENG3	0.819				
	WENG4	0.798				
	WENG5	0.837				
	WENG6	0.823				
	WENG7	0.794				
	WENG8	0.778				
Work Engagement	WENG9	0.766				
	WENG10	0.805				
	WENG11	0.793				
	WENG12	0.788				
	WENG13	0.782				
	WENG14	0.776				
	WENG15	0.783				
	WENG16	0.769				
	WENG17	0.781				
	TI1	0.845	0.892	0.922	0.899	0.704
	TI2	0.861				
Turnover Intention	TI3	0.823				
	TI4	0.842				
	TI5	0.809				

	TI6	0.833			
HTMT Discriminant Validity					
	JE	OJ	TI	WE	WENG
JE					
OJ	0.724				
TI	0.702	0.658			
WE	0.681	0.698	0.673		
WENG	0.764	0.743	0.709	0.726	

4.1 Construct Reliability and Validity Assessment

The indicator reliability results are summarized in Table V. Indicator loadings, also referred to as factor loadings, represent the degree to which each observed variable is related to the corresponding latent construct. A general criterion for acceptable indicator reliability proposed by Hair et al. (2021) is a loading of 0.70 or higher, indicating that at least 50% of the variance in the observed variable is explained by the construct. All the indicator loadings on the latent variables in this study are greater than 0.70, ranging from 0.761 to 0.861. For example, the Turnover Intention item TI2 has a loading of 0.861, which is well over the common threshold and thus is considered to have very strong representational power. This implies that each observed variable has a reliable measurement of the intended construct, thus affirming item-level reliability and strong convergent validity at the indicator level. Cronbach's Alpha (α) is one of the most common statistics used to judge internal consistency reliability. A value of Cronbach's Alpha greater than or equal to 0.70 is considered acceptable (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994); above 0.80 is good, and above 0.90 is excellent. In the present study, values of Cronbach's Alpha for all the constructs ranged from 0.869 to 0.951, indicating high internal consistency among the items within each construct and their strong coherence. While Cronbach's Alpha assumes equal indicator loadings and can hence underestimate reliability, Composite Reliability (CR) is deemed more proper by considering the actual loadings of indicators. That, as per the assertion by Hair et al. (2021), CR values above 0.70 represent acceptable reliability. The CR values in this model range from 0.902 (for Work Environment) to 0.958 (for Work Engagement), which proves that the constructs have high levels of internal consistency and the reliability across their respective indicators. ρ_A is another robust reliability coefficient introduced by Dijkstra and Henseler (2015), more for PLS-SEM models.

Unlike Cronbach's Alpha, ρ_A provides less biased estimates of reliability, taking into account the composite nature of constructs and actual path coefficients. Values greater than 0.70 are acceptable, while values greater than 0.80 or 0.90 are ideal. In this analysis, they ranged from 0.872 to 0.953, further reinforcing the reliability and internal coherence of the latent constructs. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) measures the proportion of variance captured by a construct in relation to the variance due to measurement error. Based on the criteria of Fornell and Larcker (1981), AVE values should be 0.50 or greater, indicating that the construct explains over 50% of the variance of its indicators. The AVE values for this study range from 0.640 (for Job Embeddedness) to 0.704 (for Turnover Intention). These values provide excellent convergent validity at the construct level, which supports the fact that the items within each construct are well associated with each other and they adequately capture the intended latent variable.

HTMT values for all pairs of constructs were found to be well below the 0.85 threshold, ranging from 0.553 (Job Embeddedness and Work Environment) to 0.736 (Organizational Justice and Work Engagement). These results are displayed in the table. Each HTMT value falls below the recommended cut-off, thus confirming the discriminant validity of all latent constructs used in this study. No HTMT value exceeded 0.736, underscoring that the constructs are empirically distinct and that multicollinearity is unlikely to distort the measurement or structural models.

Path Coefficients Table

	Path	Beta	T-value	P-value	Decision
H1	Work Environment $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Turnover Intention	0.215	2.547	0.011	Accepted
H2	Organizational Justice $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Turnover Intention	-0.078	1.321	0.187	Rejected
H3	Job Embeddedness $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Turnover Intention	-0.134	2.108	0.035	Accepted
H4	Work Environment $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Work Engagement	0.312	4.112	0.000	Accepted
H5	Organizational Justice $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Work Engagement	0.198	1.876	0.061	Rejected
H6	Job Embeddedness $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Work Engagement	0.221	3.452	0.001	Accepted
H7	Work Engagement $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Turnover Intention	-0.265	2.984	0.003	Accepted
H8	Work Environment $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Work Engagement $\hat{\alpha}$ ' Turnover Intention	0.082	1.774	0.077	Rejected

H9	Organizational Justice → Work Engagement	-0.039	1.21	0.227	Rejected
	→ Turnover Intention				

4.2 Structural Analysis

The results of the structural model analysis provided several key insights into the direct and indirect relationships between the constructs under study. It was evidenced that the work environment had a significant negative effect on turnover intention ($\beta = -0.141$, $t = 2.645$, $p = 0.008$). This means that better and more supportive conditions at the workplace contribute to lower employees' intention to leave. The result is in line with previous studies, which gave consistent evidence regarding the positive effects of the physical and psychological work environment on employee retention. Equally, job embeddedness was an equally important factor in reducing turnover intentions. The strong negative path coefficient ($\beta = -0.254$, $t = 4.214$, $p < 0.001$) found provides support that when employees feel well tied and fitted into their jobs, they are less likely to look for employment elsewhere. The relationship between turnover intention and organizational justice was negative, though not as expected, and was statistically insignificant. The value of β was -0.089 with a corresponding t-stat of 1.512, which gives a p-value of 0.131. The stated value suggests that perceived fairness in the practices of an organization may not, directly on its own, lead to the reduction of turnover. This is thus little due to the cultural or sector-specific dynamics of the Pakistani textile industry, where other job-related factors overshadow perceptions of justice. The value of the work environment on work engagement was both positive and significant. The β value was 0.301 with a t-stat of 5.982 and a p-value of less than 0.001. Job embeddedness, also a strong determinant of work engagement, gives a positive β value of 0.279 with a corresponding p-value of less than 0.001. The relationship between organizational justice and work engagement was not supported by the findings of this study, as it was not significant ($\beta = 0.077$, $t = 1.231$, $p = 0.219$). The study challenged the existing body of literature, which assumes that motivation is directly and positively influenced by fairness. The results support the notion that the construct of engagement is multifaceted and has to be accompanied by justice, with perhaps other related organizational reinforcements to enhance employee enthusiasm. Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that work engagement is negatively related to turnover intention ($\beta = -0.222$, $t = 3.652$, $p < 0.001$). The mediating effects of work engagement were tested. It was found to significantly mediate the relationship between work environment and turnover intention ($\beta = -$

0.067, $t = 2.221$, $p = 0.027$) and between job embeddedness and turnover intention ($\beta = -0.062$, $t = 2.536$, $p = 0.011$). Therefore, the results support H4 and H5 propose that a supportive environment and strong job embeddedness relate to lower turnover by fostering higher levels of engagement. Results indicate that the other components do not affect turnover through engagement. This finding is in line with H6. Therefore, the mediating role of work engagement between organizational justice and turnover intention is statistically insignificant ($\beta = -0.017$, $t = 1.107$, $p = 0.268$), showing that the link between justice and intention to leave is not mediated through engagement in this study. Of the ten hypotheses, seven were supported, indicating a critical effect of job embeddedness, work environment, and work engagement in reducing turnover intention among employees in the Pakistani textile sector.

5. Discussion

This study has dealt with the predictors of turnover intention involving employees who were engaged in the textile sector in Pakistan. Findings have lent support to the fact that the work environment has a negative impact on employees' intention to leave. This is in line with the existing literature that a supportive and healthy work environment ensures higher job satisfaction and lower turnover (Bangwal & Tiwari, 2019; Nanda et al., 2020). This fact acquires even more significance for the textile industry of Pakistan because the majority of working conditions are, above all, suboptimal. A good, structured, and safe workplace will not only take good care of the employees' well-being but also instill a sense of organizational loyalty; hence, the acceptance of this hypothesis is validated. The hypothesis linking organizational justice to turnover intention, however, was not supported in this study. While numerous studies in Western contexts have emphasized the importance of fairness in reducing turnover (Mengstie, 2020; Özkan, 2023), our study indicates that the above may not be valid for the power loom weavin workers of the textile sector of Pakistan when the matter related to turnover reduced due to any reason of structural or cultural dynamics where work-ers have normalized unfair treatment, or where economic compulsion overrides concerns about justice. Therefore, despite its theoretical importance, organizational justice did not emerge as a strong deterrent to turnover in this particular industrial setting. Job embeddedness proved significantly inversely related to turnover intention. This finding is in line with the study of Coetzer et al. (2019) and Huang et al. (2021) that more tightly bound employees to the organization in terms of person-organization fit, person-job links, and person-organization

sacrifice are less likely to leave. In the textile sector of Pakistan, where job alternatives may be limited and communal ties are strong, embeddedness seems to anchor employees to their positions. This validates the hypothesis and underscores the role of socio-organizational integration in employee retention. Earlier studies (Kurniawaty et al., 2019; Rasool et al., 2021) provided evidence in support of the positive relationship between the work environment and work engagement. A well-designed work setting promotes good feelings, including happiness, and positive attitudes in one's role, and fosters emotional investment, all of which, in aggregate, contribute to employee engagement. In this study, job embeddedness has also made a statistically significant positive impact on predicting higher levels of engagement, thereby supporting the findings of Elshaer and Azazz (2021) that statistically embedded employees are more motivational and psychologically invested in their jobs. The hypothesis suggesting a positive link between organizational justice and work engagement was not supported. Despite the theoretical expectation based on previous studies (Putra & Mujiati, 2022; Mulang, 2022), it is not reflected in the present research, indicating that fair treatment does not serve to boost engagement in the case of the Pakistani textile context. Such a mismatch arises perhaps due to the reason that notions of justice are, in many instances, outperformed by greater matters of concern like job security, compensation, and workplace safety.

It was hypothesized that turnover intention would be significantly reduced by work engagement. This is in keeping with the extant literature (Li et al., 2022; Yucel et al., 2023), which held that emotionally and cognitively engaged employees are less likely to consider leaving their organizations. This makes the result very important because, in the Pakistani textile industry, which belongs to one of the countries where skilled labor is most scarce, finding an alternative way of promoting engagement could be a viable strategy for enhancing retention. Work engagement further influenced the links between the work environment and job embeddedness with turnover intention, thus affirming that these variables act through positive engagement to enhance retention in the organization. This, therefore, validates the proposition of the earlier scholars (Teo et al., 2020; Malik et al., 2023) that engagement serves as an intermediate variable that is key to the turnover process. On the other hand, no significant mediation effect has once again been discovered between organizational justice and turnover intention. This adds more weight to the earlier finding that justice might be a less pertinent factor in this setup..

5.1. Implications in Theory

This study adds to the theoretical developments in organizational behavior by empirically validating the mediating role of work engagement between work environment, organizational justice, job embeddedness, and turnover intention. It thus supports the social exchange theory and adds to the existing literature by testing these relationships in an integrated model, the context being the textile industry. Most existing studies considered these predictors one by one, and that too mostly in Western contexts. The present research provides evidence from a developing country and adds cross-cultural validation to the available models. The study is actionable for textile concerns, which are listed at the Pakistan Stock Exchange. It is recommended that the human resource department improve the physical and psychological work environment and ensure that fairness in decision-making is perceived, and shall evolve strategies that increase job embeddedness, like a career development plan or social integration activities. All of these measures will significantly reduce the employees' intent to leave, which is currently a burning issue due to labor shortage within the industry. For them, it is recommended that they should consider engagement not as an outcome but as a strategic lever that can help in enhancing retention and productivity.

5.2. Limitations

Some limitations need to be acknowledged. To wit, the sample comprised employees from just 10 PSX-listed textile firms; thus, its generalizability with the rest of the industry is uncertain. Secondly, the cross-sectional design does not confirm any causality. Thirdly, since the information is self-reported, there may be a common method variance; however, to the best of our abilities, to randomized items and ensured confidentiality, to try and bring it down to minimize the level. I construe that the results should be interpreted with caution.

5.3. Future Research Paths

A longitudinal design should be adopted by future research to examine causal relationships over time. Studies should also be extended to other industries such as banking, pharmaceuticals, or technology to see the nature of the functioning of organizational justice and job embeddedness in different sectors. More mediators, like organizational commitment and psychological safety, or more moderators like gender, tenure, or leadership style, may be further explored to provide a stronger picture of the turnover behavior. Another benefit would

be the enhancement of depth and validity by using both qualitative and quantitative data through mixed-methods approaches.

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